

Re: James Lovelock (1919-2022)

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Dear Editor,

I want to thank you for this fascinating and engaging biography of James Lovelock. His work and words are an inspiration for all of us as we come out of a global pandemic. It reminds us to take better care of our fragile planet.

His work also reminds to keep our minds open to alternate views of life and intelligence elsewhere in the Universe [1,2,3].

His life should be an example for all of us.

References

1. Banerjee S. *A Roadmap for a Computational Theory of the Value of Information in Origin of Life Questions*. *Interdiscip Descr Complex Syst*. 2016;14(3):314-21. Available from: <http://indecs.eu/index.php?s=x&y=2016&p=314-321>.
2. Banerjee S. *Emergent rules of computation in the Universe lead to life and consciousness: a computational framework for consciousness*. *Interdiscip Descr Complex Syst*. 2021 mar;19(1):31-41. Available from: <http://indecs.eu/index.php?s=x&y=2021&p=31-41>
3. Banerjee S. *A Framework for Designing Compassionate and Ethical Artificial Intelligence and Artificial Consciousness*. *Interdiscip Descr Complex Syst*. 2020 may;18(2-A):85-95. Available from: <http://indecs.eu/index.php?s=x&y=2020&p=85-95>